

ISSN (p): 3030-3362

№ 2(24)

27.02.2025

IF 2024
11.7

R

TADQIQ VA TATBIQ

Research and implementation

scientific-methodical journal

S C I E N C E S

Exact, Natural, Political, Social, Economic, Technical, Medical, Pedagogical

INTERNATIONAL
STANDARD
SERIAL
NUMBER
INTERNATIONAL CENTRE

CERTIFICATE
№ 078777

ral-journal.uz

@ferteach_uz

Editor in Chief:

F.M.Mukhtarov
PhD, associate prof

Executive editor

S.I.Zokirov
PhD, associate prof

Languages:

Uzbek, Russian, English and
Karakalpak

Registered in the Agency of
Information and Mass
Communications under the
Administration of the
President of the Republic of
Uzbekistan on May 3, 2023
under number 078777.

[IF-2024: 11.7](#)

 [@feritech_uz](https://t.me/feritech_uz)

 +99893-343-13-14

 <https://rai-journal.uz>

Editorial Board:

B.R.Ismailov – Dr. Tech. Sc., Prof., M.Avezov South Kaz. Univ., Shymkent, Kazakhstan
I.Bjorn – Ph.D., Imeritus, Technical University of Denmark, Copenhagen, Denmark
A.Rasulov – Dr. Phys.-Math. Sc., Prof., TUIT Fergana Branch, Fergana, Uzbekistan
L.K.Mamadaliyeva – Dr. Tech. Sc. (DSc), Prof., FerPI, Fergana, Uzbekistan
M.E.Yunusaliyev – Dr. Tech. Sc. (DSc), Prof., FerPI, Fergana, Uzbekistan
X.B.Ismailov – Can. Tech. Sc., Assoc. Prof., M.Avezov South Kaz. Univ., Shymkent, Kazakhstan
J.T.Moldaliyev – Can. Bio. Sc., Assoc. Prof., OshSU, Osh, Kyrgyzstan
O.S.Nazarmatov – DSc in Econ., TUIT Fergana Branch, Fergana, Uzbekistan
G.K.Obidova – DSc in Ped., TUIT Fergana Branch, Fergana, Uzbekistan
T.M.Abdullayev – Ph.D. in Tech. Sc., TUIT Fergana Branch, Fergana, Uzbekistan.
N.I.Ibrokhimov – Ph.D. in Phys.-Math., TUIT Fergana Branch, Fergana, Uzbekistan.
A.R.Nurmatov – Ph.D. in History, NamSU, Fergana, Uzbekistan.
T.Yu.Bakirov – PhD in Ped. Sc., FarSU, Fergana, Uzbekistan
D.F.Tukhtasinov – Ph.D. in Ped. Sc., TUIT Fergana branch, Fergana, Uzbekistan.
S.B.Atajonova – Ph.D in Ped. Sc., AndMI, Andijan Uzbekistan
Sh.A.Umarov – Ph.D. in Phys.-Math. Sc., TUIT Fergana branch, Fergana, Uzbekistan.
I.A.Rustamov – Ph.D. in Phil. Sc., TUIT Fergana branch, Fergana, Uzbekistan.
B.Kh.Tolipov – Ph.D. in Phil. Sc., TUIT Fergana branch, Fergana, Uzbekistan.
O.Kh.Otakulov – Can. Tech. Sc., Assoc. Prof., TUIT Fergana branch, Uzbekistan
O.S.Raimjonova – Ph.D in Tech. Sc., Assoc. Prof., TUIT Fergana branch, Uzbekistan
R.A.Nuridinova – Ph.D in Tech. Sc., Assoc. Prof., TUIT Fergana branch, Uzbekistan
M.I.Ismoilov – Ph.D in Tech. Sc., Assoc. Prof., TUIT Fergana branch, Uzbekistan
I.T.Tojiboyev – Can. Tech. Sc., Assoc. Prof., Fergana State University, Uzbekistan
Sh.J.Kholmatov – Ph.D., TUIT Fergana branch, Fergana, Uzbekistan
Z.N.Khatamova – Ph.D. in Tech. Sc., TUIT Fergana branch, Fergana, Uzbekistan
Q.Kh. Akhunov – Can. Tech. Sc., Assoc. Prof., Fergana Polytechnic Institute, Uzbekistan
M.Kh. Okhunov – Can. Tech. Sc., Assoc. Prof., Fergana Polytechnic Institute, Uzbekistan
A.Q. Khomidov – Can. Tech. Sc., Assoc. Prof., Fergana Polytechnic Institute, Uzbekistan
Sh.Sh. Akramov – PhD, TUIT Fergana Branch, Fergana, Uzbekistan
A.A. Salimov – PhD in Econ., Fergana Polytechnic Institute, Uzbekistan
Z.G'. Ubaydullayev – Can. Econ., TUIT Qarchi Branch, Qarchi, Uzbekistan
S.S. Ibragimov – Ph.D in Tech. Sc., AndMI, Andijan Uzbekistan
Sh.J. Kholmatov – Ph.D. in Phil., TUIT Fergana Branch, Fergana, Uzbekistan
G.D. Kuchkarova – Ph.D. in Phil., TUIT Fergana Branch, Fergana, Uzbekistan
I.R.Teshabayeva – Ph.D. in Tech. Sc., TUIT Fergana Branch, Fergana, Uzbekistan
A.L.Meliqzuyev – Ph.D. in Phil. Sc., TUIT Fergana Branch, Fergana, Uzbekistan
O.U.Kholmatova – Ph.D. in Phil. Sc., TUIT Fergana Branch, Fergana, Uzbekistan
N.N.Radjabov – Ph.D. in Phil. Sc., Assoc. Prof., Oriental University, Tashkent, Uzbekistan
Sh.A.Yuldashov – Ph.D. in Tech. Sc., Fergana State University, Fergana, Uzbekistan
A.A.Yuldashev – Ph.D. in Tech. Sc., Fergana State University, Fergana, Uzbekistan
M.Israilov – Can. Tech. Sc., Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan Academy of Forces
N.S.Abdullaeva – PhD in Ped. Sc., NamDU, Namangan, Uzbekistan
A.G.Turgunboeva – PhD in Ped. Sc., NamDPI, Namangan, Uzbekistan
M.A.Abdullaeva – Prof., NamDU, Namangan, Uzbekistan
I.O.Ergashev – PhD in Econ., Fiscal Institute, Tashkent, Uzbekistan
N.T.Mamatxanova – PhD in Ped. Sc., NamDPI, Namangan, Uzbekistan
U.Yu.Akhundzhanov – PhD in Tech. Sc., TUIT Fergana Branch, Fergana, Uzbekistan
O.M.Ergashev – PhD in Tech. Sc., TUIT Fergana Branch, Fergana, Uzbekistan
N.R.Khallieva – PhD in Econ., Bukhara MTI, Bukhara, Uzbekistan
F.K.Achilova – Can. Econ. Sc., TUIT Qarchi Branch, Qarchi, Uzbekistan
A.K.Samyayev – PhD in Geog., Sam. Reg. Ped. Skills Center, Samarkand, Uzbekistan
J.S.Abdullayev – Can. Phys.-Math. Sc., Assoc. Prof., TUIT Fergana branch, Uzbekistan

Bosh muharrir:

F.M.Mukhtarov
PhD, dotsent

Ijrochi muharrir:

S.I.Zokirov
PhD, dotsent

Nashr tillari:

O'zbek, Rus, Inzliz va
Qoraqalpoq

O'zbekiston Respublikasi
Prezidenti Administratsiyasi
huzuridagi Axborot va
ommaviy
kommunikatsiyalar agentligi
tomonidan 2023-yil 3-
mayda 078777 raqami bilan
ro'yxatga olingan..

IF-2024: 11.7

 [@feriteach_uz](https://t.me/feriteach_uz)
 +99893-343-13-14
 <https://rai-journal.uz>

Editorial Board:

B.R.Ismailov – t.f.d., prof. M.Avezov Jan. Qoz. Univ-ti., Chimkent, Qozog'iston
I.Byorno - Ph.D., Imeritus, Daniya Texnika Universiteti, Kopengagen, Daniya
A.Rasulov – f.-m.f.d., prof.TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston
L.K.Mamadaliyeva – t.f.d. (DSc), prof. FarPI, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston
M.E.Yunusaliyev – t.f.d. (DSc), prof. FarPI, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston
X.B.Ismailov- t.f.n., dot., M.Avezov Jan. Qoz. Univ-ti., Chimkent, Qozog'iston
J.T.Moldaliyev - bio. f. n., dotsent. OshDU, Osh, Qirg'iziston
O.S.Nazarmatov - iqt.f.d. DSc, TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston
G.K.Obidova - ped.f.d. DSc, TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston
T.M.Abdullayev – t.f.b. Ph.D., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.
N.I.Ibrokhimov – f.-m.f.b. Ph.D., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.
A.R.Nurmatov – tarix f.b. Ph.D., NamDU, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.
T.Yu.Bakirov - ped. f.b. PhD, FarDU, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston
D.F.To'xtasinov - ped.f.b. Ph.D., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.
S.B.Atajonova - ped.f.b. Ph.D, AndMI, Andijon O'zbekiston
Sh.A.Umarov - f.-m.f.b. Ph.D., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.
I.A.Rustamov - fal.f.b. Ph.D., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.
B.X.Tolipov - ff.b. Ph.D., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.
O.X.Otaqulov – t.f.n., dotsent. TATU Farg'ona filiali, O'zbekiston
O.S.Raimjonova – t.f.b. Ph.D, dotsent, TATU Farg'ona filiali, O'zbekiston
R.A.Nurdinova – t.f.b. Ph.D, dotsent, TATU Farg'ona filiali, O'zbekiston
M.I.Ismoilov – t.f.b. Ph.D, dotsent, TATU Farg'ona filiali, O'zbekiston
I.T.Tojiboyev – t.f.n., dotsent, Farg'ona davlat universiteti, O'zbekiston
Sh.J.Kholmatov - i.i.f.b. PhD., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston
Z.N.Khatamova - t.f.b. PhD., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston
Q.X. Axunov - t.f.n., dotsent, Farg'ona politexnika instituti, O'zbekiston
M.X. Oxunov - t.f.n., dotsent, Farg'ona politexnika instituti, O'zbekiston
A.Q.Xomidov - t.f.n., dotsent, Farg'ona politexnika instituti, O'zbekiston
Sh.Sh.Akramov – q.x.f.b. PhD, TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston
A.A.Salimov - iqt.f.b. PhD, Farg'ona politexnika instituti, O'zbekiston
Z.G'.Ubaydullayev - iqt.f.n., TATU Qarchi filiali, Qarchi, O'zbekiston
S.S.Ibragimov - t.f.b. Ph.D, AndMI, Andijon O'zbekiston
Sh.J.Xolmatov- fal.f.b. Ph.D., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston
G.D.Kuchkarova- fal.f.b. Ph.D., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston
I.R.Teshabayeva - t.f.b. Ph.D., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston
A.L.Meliquziyev- fil.f.b. Ph.D., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston
O.U.Xolmatova- fil.f.b. Ph.D., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston
N.N.Radjabov- fil.f.b. Ph.D., dotsent, Oriental University, Toshkent, O'zbekiston
Sh.A.Yuldashov - t.f.b. Ph.D., Farg'ona davlat universiteti, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston
A.A.Yuldashev - t.f.b. Ph.D., Farg'ona davlat universiteti, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston
M.Israilov - t.f.n., O'zbekiston Respublikasi Qurolli Kuchlar Akademiyasi
N.S.Abdullayeva - p.f.b. PhD, NamDU, Namangan, O'zbekiston
A.G.Turg'unboyeva - p.f.b. PhD, NamDPI, Namangan, O'zbekiston
M.A.Abdullayeva - professor, NamDU, Namangan, O'zbekiston
I.O.Ergashev – iqt.f.b. PhD, Fiskal instituti, Toshkent, O'zbekiston
N.T.Mamatxanova - p.f.b. PhD, NamDPI, Namangan, O'zbekiston
U.Yu.Axundjanov - t.f.b. PhD, TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston
O.M.Ergashev - t.f.b. PhD, TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston
N.R.Xallieva - iqt.f.b. PhD, Buxoro MTI, Buxoro, O'zbekiston
F.K.Achilova - iqt.f.n., TATU Qarchi filiali, Qarchi, O'zbekiston
A.K.Samyayev - g.f.b. PhD, Sam. vil. ped. mah. mar, Samarqand, O'zbekiston
J.S.Abdullayev - f.-m.f.n., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.

Abdulla Oripovning portret yaratish mahorati

¹ Buriyeva Firuza, ² Ibrohimova Muxabbat

¹ *O‘zbekiston-Finlandiya pedagogika instituti, katta o‘qituvchisi, PhD*

² *O‘zbekiston-Finlandiya pedagogika instituti, 2-bosqich talabasi*

Copyright: © 2025 by the author.

Licensee: This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada o‘zbek adabiyotining zabardast vakili, O‘zbekiston Qahramoni, mohir tarjimon va jamoat arbobi bo‘lmish Abdulla Oripov hayoti va faoliyati haqida qisqacha ma’lumot, uning ijodining boshqa yozuvchi va shoirlar ijodidan ajralib turuvchi o‘ziga xos xususiyatlari, xususan, ijodkorning portret yaratishning usullari to‘g‘risida so‘z yuritiladi. Shuningdek, shoir she‘riyatida ona Vatanga bo‘lgan muhabbat tuyg‘usining ustunligi, uning haqiqatgo‘yiligi, xalqqa sodiqligi, vatanparvarligi, insonparvarligi kabi insoniy jihatlari haqida ham fikrlar mavjud.

Kalit so‘zlar: she‘r, portret, shoir, adabiyot, she‘riyat, ijod, Vatan, ona.

Received: 03 Feb. 2025

Accepted: 05 Feb. 2025

Published: 06 Feb 2025

Ma’lumki, O‘zbekiston Qahramoni bo‘lmish Abdulla Oripov o‘zining boy ma’naviy merosi bilan o‘zbek adabiyoti va she‘riyatida o‘ziga xos o‘chmas iz qoldirdi. O‘zbek she‘riyatini ulkan imorat desak Abdulla Oripov mana shunday muhtasham imoratning bunyod bo‘lishiga o‘z hissasini qo‘shgan ya’ni o‘z qo‘li bilan g‘isht qo‘ygan desak mubolag‘a bo‘lmaydi. Uning ijodining o‘ziga xos xususiyati shundaki, katta-yu kichikka birdek tushunarli, har bitta jumlada olam-olam ma’noni anglash mumkin, she‘rlarida vatanga cheksiz mehr-muhabbat, onalarga, ayollarga hurmat-ehtirom, yurtga sodiqlik, insoniylik, do‘stlik, tinchliksevarlik, millatparvarlik, eng go‘zal mavzulardan bo‘lgan sevgi-muhabbat va shu kabi tuyg‘ular yaqqol aks etib turadi.

Dastlab ijodkorning kechirgan turmushiga, bolalik chog‘lariga nazar tashlaydigan bo‘lsak, yoshligi Qo‘ng‘irtov etaklarida o‘tgan, qishloqdagi tengdoshlari qatori qo‘y boqdi, suv tashidi, pichan o‘rdi, somon to‘pladi, yer chopdi. Hech kim tug‘ilgandan mashhur bo‘lib qolmaganidek, to‘xtovsiz harakat, tinimsiz mehnat, turmush mashaqqatlari, sabr-qanoat, so‘nmas shijoat, intilish uni ana shunday sharaflil nomga erishishiga, xalqning hurmat-e‘tiborini qozonishiga, elning suygan shoiri bo‘lib yetishishiga sabab bo‘ldi. Shu bo‘lmi shoir she‘riyatida milliy ruh, xalqchillik ustuvor xususiyatidir. Ijodkor o‘z xalqining dardini teran angladi, garchi lirik asarlarda bo‘lsa-da, ular qiyofasini g‘oyat haqqoniy tasvirlay oldi. Aslida portret, peyzaj,

xronotop kabi badiiy vositalar biror bir adabiy turga oid janrlarda ishlatilishi lozimligi haqida biror bir nazariy qoida belgilab qo'yilmagan. Hatto lirikaning ayrim shakllarining bosh belgisipersonajlilik ekanligi ham bizga ma'lumdir. Bu haqda "Adabiy turlar va janrlar" risolasida batafsil keltirilib, "lirikaning meditatif lirika, simvolik lirika, personajli lirika, voqeaband lirika kabi ko'rinishlari sanab o'tilgan" [2.505].

Abdulla Oripov she'rlarida voqeabandlik ham, personajlilik ham yetakchidir. Shoirning aynan shu kabi she'rlarida uning portret yaartish mahorati namoyon bo'ladi. Shoir asarlaridagi ko'plab insonlar portreti orqali kitobxonning ko'z o'ngida turli zamon va muhit, ijtimoiy hayot tasvirini gavdalanantira oladi. Misol uchun "Ayol" she'rini keltiraylik:

Yigitlar maktubin bitganda qondan,

Kelinlar firoqdan chekkanda yohu,

Unig ham panohi qaytmadi jangdan,

O'n to'qqiz yoshida beva qoldi u.

"Ayol" she'ri ana shunday sermazmun band bilan boshlanadi. Endi quyidagi bandga e'tibor qaratamiz:

Qaqragan lablarda olovli nafas,

Kechalar kechmishin ayladi ko'mir.

Parishon sochlari yor ko'ksi emas,

Muzdayin bolishda qoldi bir umr.

Birgina yosh ayolning tasviri orqali urushning naqadar berahm ekanligini, qanchadan qancha odamlarning yostig'ini quritganini, yosh oilalarning ajralib ketishiga sabab bo'lganligini ko'rishimiz mumkin. Mazkur she'r urushga ketgan amakilarining bevalariga bag'ishlab yozilgan. Shoirning "Onajon" deb nomlangan she'ri ham eng tasirlilaridan biridir. She'r quyidagi jummlalar bilan boshlanadi :

Necha kunki yo'q oromim

Kelolmayman hushimga.

Onajonim kechalari

Kirib chiqar tushimga.

Abdulla Oripov mazkur she'rini onasi Turdi Karvon qizining xotirasiga bag'ishlab yozgan. She'rni o'qir ekanmiz, ko'z o'ngimizda Abdullaning tushida onasi bilan qilgan suhbatlari, unga aytgan nasihatlari gavdalanadi. Dunyoda shoirman degan zot borki, o'zining eng samimiy, eng go'zal satrlarini onalariga bag'ishlab yozadi. Bu kabi jummlalar dil tubidagi eng aziz xotiralarni uyg'otishga qodir. Abdulla Oripovning onasiga atalgan bu she'ri ham shulardan biridir desak adashmaymiz.

Abdulla Oripov she'riyatining o'ziga xosliklaridan biri haqiqatgo'ylikdir. Shoir she'riyati haqqoniy bo'lganligi bilan birga mavzu doirasi keng, mazmuni esa boy va teran. Ijodi davomida eng katta e'tiborini ona Vatan-O'zbekiston mavzusiga qaratgan. Vataniga, millatiga va xalqiga bo'lgan muhabbat tuyg'usi shoir ijodining asosini tashkil etadi. Fikrimizning dalili sifatida "O'zbekiston" qasidasini keltirishimiz mumkin. Shuningdek, shoirning butun dunyoga mashhur bo'lgan diyorimiz madhiyasi muallifi ekanligi ham uning Vatan tuyg'usini eng bebaho va muqaddas qadriyat sifatida e'zozlashidan darak beradi. She'rlarida Vatan va onaning umumlashma obrazini yaratadi ya'ni insonning dunyoda onasi bitta bo'lgani singari uning Vatani ham bittadir:

Bisyor bo'lsa agar bol ham beqadr,
Takror aytilganda rangsizdir kalom.
Bu yorug' olamda Vatan bittadir,
Bittadir dunyoda ona degan nom.

Abdulla Oripovning asosiy tasvir obyekti — O'zbekiston, asosiy qahramoni esa mehnatkash o'zbek xalqidir. Shoirning o'zi bu haqiqatni: «Men kuylayman bu olam aro, mag'rur turgan xalqimni faqat», — deb qayd etgan edi. Chindan ham, shoir o'z ijodida bu ilhombaxsh mavzuga qayta-qayta murojaat etadi va har gal bir-biridan nodir, go'zal asarlar yozib, O'zbekiston va o'zbek xalqi hayotining yangi-yangi qirralarini ochib beradi. Xalqning mehnatsevarlik, insonparvarlik, vatanparvarlik, bunyodkorlik, bag'rikenglik singari xislatlarini maftun bo'lib tasvirlash orqali millatning yaxlit obrazini yaratadi. O'zbek xalqining milliy xarakterini mehr-muhabbat va g'urur bilan chizib beradi:

Yulduzlar, bilmaysiz mening xalqimni,
Bundayin zahmatkash yer yuzida kam.
Elda tinim bordir, unda tinim yo'q,
Shunday ishparastdir, u munisginam.[1.383-384]

Abdulla Oripov mehribon onajonlar, aziz opa-singillar, otalar obrazini yaratish bilan birga ustozlari haqida yozishni ham unutmagan:

Muallim haqida so'zim ushbu dir:
Muallim kamolot ichra ko'zgudir.
O'qidim Gerodot, tarixni ko'p bor,
Forobiy, Danteni takror va takror.
Barini o'qidim, lol qoldi aqlim,
Bariga ustozsan o'zing, muallim.

Haqiqatan ham, bu dunyoda ustoz kabi ulug' zot yo'qdir. Shoir ushbu she'rda ta'kidlaganidek, Gerodot, Forobiy, Dante kabi aql egalarining butun jahonga

mashhur bo‘lishiga ustozlarining hissasi kattadir. Shuning uchun ham xalqimiz orasida “Ustoz otangdek ulug‘” degan naql bor.

Abdulla Oripov she‘riyati hayot bilan hamnafas, rostgo‘y, xalqchil va kurashchan she‘riyatdir. Shoir dolzarb g‘oyalarni olg‘a surishda, ko‘pchilikni hayajonga soladigan katta fikrlarni, turfa tuyg‘ularni ifodalashda Qur‘oni Karim va hadis Sharif ohanglaridan ham o‘rinli foydalanadi. Shoirning «Haj daftari»,

«Hadis sadolari» she‘riy to‘plamlari buning dalilidir. Xususan, ellikta hadisona she‘rida shoir diniy libosda namoyon bo‘lgan ezgu tuyg‘ularni, milliy qadriyatlarimizni ixlos bilan tasvirlab bergan[1.389]. Misol uchun “Alloh dargohi” deb nomlangan she‘rdan parcha keltiraylik:

Necha ming musulmon tunu kun uyg‘oq,
Ka‘ba atrofini tinmay aylanar,
Murodi tabarruk maskanni o‘pmoq
Sajdaga har biri har zum shaylanar.[3.5]

Shoirning aytishicha: “ Makkai mukarramaga borganimning dastlabki kunida Ka‘batullohda—Ollah uyi yonida tunni bedor o‘tkazib, tilovat bilan bir qatorda baytlar yoza boshladim. Men bu holatga avvaldan bir muncha tayyor bo‘lganim sabablimi satrlarim o‘z-o‘zidan quyilib kelaverdilar. She‘riy hadislarimning barchasi payg‘ambarimiz Muhammad alayhissalom suxanlari bilan bevosita bog‘liq edi”.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar:

- 1.1.Sadulla Mirzayev. “XX asr o‘zbek adabiyoti”.Toshkent: “Yangi asr avlodi”-2005.
- 2.2. Feruza Buriyeva.Xurshid Davronning individual poetik uslubi. Oriental Renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences. VOLUME 2 / ISSUE 12. ISSN 2181-1784 Scientific Journal Impact Factor SJIF 2022:5.947.December –2022. P.500-507
- 3.3.Abdulla Oripov. “Haj daftari”(Ellik hadis).Toshkent.1992.

Scientific-methodical journal “Research and implementation”

Address:

150100, Fergana region, Fergana, Solim street, 23/4, apt. 26

E-mail:

chief_editor@rai-journal.uz

Our website:

<https://rai-journal.uz/>

The Scientific-methodical journal “Research and implementation” was founded by LLC Fer-Teach and supported by the Fergana branch of the Tashkent University of Information Technologies named after Muhammad al-Khorezmi. This journal was registered by the Agency of Information and Mass Communications under the Administration of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on May 3, 2023 (No 078777).

ISSN 3030-3362.

"Research and implementation" is a specialized journal in the field of technology and covers all major areas of research and development in various fields of technical sciences: physics, mathematics, information technology. The journal also publishes scientific articles on linguistics, teaching methods and the history of the development of technical sciences.

Languages: Uzbek, Russian, English, Karakalpak

ВНИМАНИЕ!

При использовании материалов журнала необходимо указывать источник. Авторы статей несут ответственность за содержание статей и за сам факт их публикации.

Редакция не всегда разделяет мнения авторов и не несет ответственности за недостоверность публикуемых данных.

Редакция журнала не несет никакой ответственности перед авторами и/или третьими лицами и организациями за возможный ущерб, вызванный публикацией статьи.

ATTENTION!

When using journal materials, you must indicate the source.

The authors of the articles are responsible for the content of the articles and for the very fact of their publication.

The editors do not always share the opinions of the authors and are not responsible for the unreliability of the published data.

The editorial board of the journal does not bear any responsibility to the authors and / or third parties and organizations for possible damage caused by the publication of the article

DIQQAT!

Jurnal materiallaridan foydalanganda manbani ko'rsatish kerak.

Maqola mualliflari maqolalar mazmuni va ularning nashr etilishi fakti uchun javobgardirlar.

Har doim ham mualliflarning fikrlari tahririyat nuqtai nazarini ifodalamaydi va nashr etilgan ma'lumotlarning haqiqiyliги uchun javobgar emas.

Jurnal tahririyati mualliflar va/yoki uchinchi shaxslar va tashkilotlarga maqolaning e'lon qilinishi natijasida yetkazilishi mumkin bo'lgan zarar uchun javobgar emas.